

Chemistry of platinum and iridium complexes of thioethers : contributions of P. C. Rây and related later developments

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Abstract : The platinum species studied include planar $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and octahedral $[\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ both of which occur in *cis* and *trans* isomeric forms. Rây's work concerned their synthesis (from $\text{H}_2\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}\text{Cl}_6$ and R_2S , $\text{R} = \text{Et}$, also Me , CH_2Ph) and reactivity towards amine ligands as well as assignment of isomeric structure. Others including Werner had worked in this area prior to Rây. However the correct assignment of isomeric structure could only be settled later by others through application of physical tools. Rây also examined $[\text{PtCl}_3.2\text{R}_2\text{S}]$ which he correctly identified as a mixed valence compound which he formulated as a loose 1 : 1 combination of $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_4]$. However, it is more likely that it has the ionic structure $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_4][\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}\text{Cl}_6]$ proposed earlier by Tschugaeff. The first-ever thioether coordination chemistry of iridium originated from Rây's laboratory. By reacting IrCl_4 with R_2S he isolated two (yellow and red) isomeric compounds of formula $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_3\text{Cl}_3]$ and studied their reactions with pyridine. He assigned *fac* and *mer* geometries to the yellow and red forms respectively. However physical tools revealed decades later that the yellow isomer actually has *mer* geometry and the red isomer is an ionic dimerization isomer $[\text{Ir}^{\text{IV}}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_4\text{Cl}_2][\text{Ir}^{\text{II}}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_4]$. The $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_3(\text{R}_2\text{S})_3]$ system of Rây was the first member of the general class $[\text{M}^{\text{III}}\text{X}_3(\text{R}_2\text{S})_3]$ (M is 4d or 5d metal and X is Cl or Br) discovered by others later. All appear to have *mer* geometry.

Keywords : Thioether complexes, platinum (bi-, tetra- and mixed-valent), trivalent iridium, geometrical isomerism, dimerization isomerism.

Introduction

Following his seminal work on the chemistry of nitrates¹ in Presidency College, Rây's major research interest started shifting towards the virgin field of sulfur ligands and their coordination compounds from 1914. And this became the top arena of activity of his group through most of his active years at the College of Science (1916-1936). The facilities available to him were limited, yet he had to face daunting problems of purification and characterization in the sulfur chemistry work². But his intuition, insight and perseverance helped him to overcome the difficulties in most cases heralding abiding progress in the field and he became an early pioneer of sulfur-ligand based coordination chemistry of heavier transition metals specially of mercury, gold, platinum and iridium. The cases of mercury and gold in relation to ligands like thiols, thioethers and thiourea were chronicled in a previous paper². In this work we scrutinize Rây's notable contributions to platinum and iridium chemistry, his main

concern being thioether ligands.

Platinum complexes

General observations :

This activity is chronicled in a series of papers published during 1919-1934. In the absence of sufficient structural information the complexes of thiols^{3,4} which can now be presumed to be polymeric⁵ will not be discussed any further. The same applies to the polynuclear complexes $(\text{Pt}_2\text{-Pt}_{19})^{6-8}$ afforded by dialkyl disulfides in conjunction with amines and halides.

Our primary focus shall be on the work concerning synthesis, isomerism and ligand substitution reactions of platinum-thioether complexes of three compositional types : $[\text{PtCl}_2.2\text{R}_2\text{S}]$, $[\text{PtCl}_4.2\text{R}_2\text{S}]$ and $[\text{PtCl}_3.2\text{R}_2\text{S}]$. Relevant later work by others, specially on structural aspects, will be cited.

The bivalent family :

Blomstrand reported in the 1880's that alkyl thioethers

like Me_2S afford mixed complexes of bivalent platinum of type $[\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{R}_2\text{S}]$ which occur in two isomeric forms – one bright yellow (α -isomer) and the other nearly white or very light lemon yellow (β -isomer) in colour. He conjectured about their structures in terms of his chain theory of coordination compounds. In 1893 Werner intuitively suggested that the two were geometrical isomers of planar four-coordinate bivalent platinum and assigned *cis* (**1a**) and *trans* (**1b**) configuration to the α and β forms respectively.

Rây used chloroplatinic acid, $\text{H}_2\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}\text{Cl}_6$ as the platinum starting material in his synthetic work. In 1923 he reported⁴ the isolation of $[\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}]$ by reacting H_2PtCl_6 with Et_2S in ethanol. Subsequently he examined the reaction in greater detail in aqueous media and isolated⁹ both the α and β forms of the complex having colours and m.p. (108° for both) as reported earlier. In this synthesis, the tetravalent metal is reduced to the bivalent state by the thioether ligand. He accepted Werner's proposal on isomers' structure⁹.

But Werner's proposal (**1a**, **1b**) of isomeric structure itself was not based on any solid experimental foundation and the controversy about the structure of the isomers continued into the 1930's and alternative suggestions kept on coming¹⁰. Finally X-ray work ($\text{R} = \text{Me}$) revealed that the α -form has the *trans* structure **1b**¹¹. Subsequent solution dipole moment data corroborated this and also showed that the β -isomer had the *cis* geometry **1a**¹². The coordinated sulfur atom has pyramidal geometry whose inversion has been studied^{13,14} for both **1a** and **1b**. A standardized synthesis of both isomers ($\text{R} = \text{Et}$) from K_2PtCl_4 and Et_2S is available¹⁵.

In addition to the α and β forms, Rây claimed the isolation of four more isomers of $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ which differed in shades of colour and in melting points (77° – 110°C)⁹. Since the melting point of either of the geometrical isomers is sensitive to the presence of impurities

including the other isomer^{10,15}, it is likely that the four extra isomers reported were merely contaminated *cis* or *trans* isomers. Rây did not propose structures for the extra isomers. In the 1920's when he did the work, structural concepts about complex compounds were still quite fuzzy in spite of the arrival of Werner's theory (1893). Existence of too many isomers may not have appeared strange at that time.

Facile substitution reactions of the $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ isomers by donor bases like NH_3 , EtNH_2 , pyridine (py) etc. were examined by Rây¹⁶. The products were four-coordinate complexes like $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{EtNH}_2)_4\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Pt}(\text{py})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{py})_4\text{Cl}_2]$. He also prepared complexes of Me_2S and $(\text{PhCH}_2)_2\text{S}$ of platinum and studied their substitution reaction with bases^{17,18}.

The tetravalent family :

By setting aside a concentrated solution of Et_2S and H_2PtCl_6 in ethanol for two or three days Rây isolated a yellow crystalline complex of tetravalent platinum having the composition $[\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}]$ and m.p. 198°C . It was nonelectrolytic in acetone solution and monomeric in freezing benzene^{4,9}. He examined certain crystallographic aspects like crystal system, habit, cleavage, optical properties etc. and confirmed the tight binding of the chloride ligand in solution by observing that silver nitrate produced very little of silver chloride precipitate⁹. It was found that NH_3 displaces thioether and a part of chloride affording $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}_2$ while pyridine yielded $[\text{Pt}(\text{py})_2\text{Cl}_4]$. Aniline was found to reduce the metal to the bivalent state yielding $[\text{Pt}(\text{PhNH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ in two isomeric forms¹⁶. Rây noted that $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ was first reported by the French chemist A. Loir in 1853⁹.

He represented the compound as a hexacoordinated Werner complex but did not specify whether it had *cis*, **2a** or *trans*, **2b** configuration⁴. Later in 1930 the same complex (m.p. 198°C) was prepared by others via oxidation of α - $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ by chlorine in solution. An isomer (m.p. 135°C) similarly resulted from oxidation of β - $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ ^{10,19}. Spectral data revealed that the two isomers respectively have *trans*, **2b** (m.p. 198°C) and *cis*, **2a** (m.p. 135°C) geometry²⁰. Thus Rây's yellow $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ had *trans* geometry. The bright yellow

low crystalline methyl analogue $[\text{Pt}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ was also synthesized via degradation of a mixed-valence compound (see below) and its reactions with bases studied¹⁸.

Mixed valence species :

By suitably manipulating the reaction between H_2PtCl_6 and Et_2S , an orange yellow complex of composition $[\text{PtCl}_3.2\text{Et}_2\text{S}]$ was isolated. Rây found it to be transformed into a mixture of $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ upon boiling in ethanol. He also prepared $[\text{PtCl}_3.2\text{Me}_2\text{S}]$ which behaved similarly¹⁸. The observations led him to propose⁹ that the formula $[\text{PtCl}_3.2\text{R}_2\text{S}]$ should be doubled, the system actually being a 1 : 1 molecular compound of the bivalent and tetravalent species as depicted in **3a** (isomeric nature of the components not specified). This constitution is reminiscent of the mixed valence amines of type $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Br}_2][\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Br}_4]$ which received considerable attention during 1960's²¹.

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The $[\text{PtCl}_3.2\text{Me}_2\text{S}]$ complex had been prepared and studied in detail earlier by Tschugaeff who proposed the constitution **3b** again based on formula doubling and valence mixing. In **3a** both coordination spheres are electroneutral and have Cl^- and R_2S ligands while **3b** is a salt where ligands are segregated between the cationic (only R_2S ligand) and the anionic (only Cl^- ligand) sites. Rây refuted **3b** in favour of **3a** on two grounds. First is the isolation of the two separated components as noted above. Second is the reaction of the complex with bases which gave him the same product as pure $[\text{Pt}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ does. For example NH_3 afforded $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{Cl}_2$ ¹⁶.

But these arguments could be flawed. The formation of separated components under relatively drastic conditions (boiling solvents etc.) does not necessarily signify their presence in the original compound. For example the cation and anion in **3b** could undergo ligand redistribution generating the components. In reaction with bases, no product corresponding to $[\text{Pt}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_4]$ was ever isolated¹⁶. In the case of NH_3 , $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{Cl}_2$ could arise from $[\text{Pt}(\text{R}_2\text{S})_4]^{2+}$ in **3b**, the chloride anion coming from $[\text{PtCl}_6]^{2-}$. One experiment which could have given strong support to Rây's proposal (**3a**) was to reconstitute " $[\text{PtCl}_3.2\text{R}_2\text{S}]$ " by mixing and evaporating the two pure components in solution under mild conditions. No such experiment, however, appears to have been reported. The balance of available informations^{9,16-18,22} taken collectively would seem to favour Tschugaeff's **3b** over Rây's **3a**.

Tschugaeff had earlier authenticated^{11,23} the pink salt $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_4][\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}\text{Cl}_6]$ which is actually a dimerization isomer of $[\text{Pt}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_2\text{Cl}_2]$. The $[\text{Pt}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})_4]^{2+}$ moiety incorporating the planar PtS_4 coordination sphere has been structurally authenticated in certain salts²⁴. The thiourea complex $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}(\text{SC}(\text{NH}_2)_4)\text{Cl}_2]$ has the same coordination sphere²⁵ and the yellow salt $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}\{\text{SC}(\text{NH}_2)_2\}_4][\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}\text{Cl}_6]$ is also well characterized²⁶. By reacting thiourea with H_2PtCl_6 Rây isolated in 1919 a yellow complex which he formulated as the thiolate $[\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}\{\text{SC}(\text{NH})(\text{NH}_2)_2\}_2\text{Cl}_2].\text{HCl}$ on the basis of elemental analysis³. He was assuming the tautomerization of thiourea into the thiol form, $\text{HSC}(\text{NH})(\text{NH}_2)$, before metal binding. Comparison of the properties of this compound³ with those of the yellow salt²⁶ noted above strongly suggests that the two are one and the same compound. After formula doubling and adding two hydrogen atoms, Rây's complex is readily recast as $[\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}\{\text{SC}(\text{NH}_2)_2\}_4][\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}\text{Cl}_6]$.

Thioether complexes of trivalent iridium

Synthesis of isomers :

The chemistry of this family was developed during 1932-36 and constitute an excellent example to illustrate Rây's early contributions towards the advancement of platinum metal chemistry of sulfur ligands. Upon treating iridium tetrachloride (IrCl_4) with dialkyl sulfides (R_2S)

he found the metal to be reduced to the trivalent state with concomitant loss of chlorine and binding of R_2S affording a compound of composition $[IrCl_3, 3R_2S]$. It was isolated in two isomeric forms differing in colour and in solubility in organic solvents. The more soluble isomer²⁷ was orange (more appropriately yellow, see below) in colour while the less soluble isomer²⁸ was coloured red. The three cases viz. $R = Me, Et$ and $PhCH_2$ were examined but detailed studies were limited to the Et species.

The synthetic reaction was found to proceed well in alcohol and acetone but was inhibited in chloroform and benzene. The high redox stability of $[IrCl_3, 3Et_2S]$ ensured its formation even when dilute aqua regia was added to the reaction mixture. Rây also briefly reported the formation of the $[IrCl_3, 3Et_2S]$ isomers by the reaction of Et_2S with ammonium hexachloroiridate $((NH_4)_2IrCl_6)^{28}$. Because of the interest these isomers aroused among inorganic chemists later, a carefully standardized synthesis of these based on the above iridate starting material was published in 1963 where it was also pointed out that the colour of Rây's 'orange' isomer is better described as yellow²⁹. In what follows we shall qualify colours accordingly.

Proposed geometrical structures :

On the basis of composition, stability and nonelectrolytic nature of the yellow isomer in acetone solution Rây promptly concluded that it is a hexacoordinated coordination compound of type $[IrCl_3(Et_2S)_3]^{27}$. Though no

solution electrical conductivity measurements appear to have been made on the red isomer he asserted that it is also similarly constituted and went further to assign *cis (fac)* and *trans (mer)* geometries **4a** and **4b** to the yellow and red isomers respectively²⁸. This he did merely on the basis of the observed colours of certain other geometrically isomeric iridium compounds as described by Delepine.

By reacting the yellow isomer with pyridine (py) he isolated $[IrCl_3(Et_2S)_2(py)]$ and $[IrCl_3(Et_2S)(py)_2]$ and assigned *fac* geometry to both in view of their orange-yellow colours²⁸. In other words he was suggesting stereoretentive substitution of Et_2S by py in **4a** in a progressive manner. Later he also studied the successful partial/complete replacement of Et_2S in yellow $[IrCl_3(Et_2S)_3]$ by ammonia and ethylamine^{30,31}.

Later work : actual nature of the isomers :

Even though assignment of isomer geometry on the basis of colour alone is inherently unsatisfactory, the proposed *fac* geometry **4a** of the yellow form had a dominant influence in defining the geometry as other $[MCl_3(Et_2S)_3]$ ($M = Rh, Ru$) species that were investigated later by others. Thus the X-ray powder patterns of the Rh and Ru species were closely alike to that of the Ir complex and on this ground *fac* geometry was assigned to both of them³². This assertion was further strengthened by the fact that this geometry for yellow $[IrCl_3(Et_2S)_3]$

was reported to be consistent with its proton nmr spectrum³³. However in the same work it was convincingly demonstrated with the help of electrical conductivity, electrophoretic, UV-Vis and NMR spectral as well as chemical data that the red form was *not* the *mer* isomer **4b** at all but is actually a 1 : 1 electrolytic salt --- the dimerization isomer $[IrCl_2(Et_2S)_4][IrCl_4(Et_2S)_2]$, **5**, where both the cation and the anion have *trans* geometry³³.

For the yellow isomer *fac* remained the well accepted geometry for years till it was shown^{34,35} in 1971 that the NMR spectrum reported earlier³³ had inadequate resolution and the properly resolved spectrum conclusively demonstrated that yellow $[IrCl_3(Et_2S)_3]$ actually had the *mer* geometry **4b**. This geometry has no symmetry (nonequivalent Et_2S ligands) unlike the *fac* geometry which has a three-fold axis of symmetry (equivalent Et_2S ligands).

In the same year ESR data showed that $[\text{RuCl}_3(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_3]$ is also *mer*³⁶. More recently $[\text{OsBr}_3(\text{R}_2\text{S})_3]$ type compounds were reported and shown to have *mer* geometry on the basis of X-ray structural studies³⁷.

Concluding remarks

Rây's original proposals on isomer geometry of the iridium thioether species did not survive. The true nature of yellow isomer which he thought to be *fac* actually turned out to be *mer* **4b** and the red isomer thought to be *mer* was actually the salt **5**, a dimerization isomer having the same composition as the yellow complex. But it is Rây's original synthetic work that brought the interesting compounds to light very early and set the ball rolling. Eventually this generated much interest and led to work in major laboratories involving modern physical tools which revealed their true nature. In the history of the now-well-known $[\text{MX}_3(\text{R}_2\text{S})_3]$ family where M is a heavier (**4d**, **5d**) transition element and X is usually Cl or Br, Rây with his iridium work remains an original torch bearer.

On the other hand in the case of platinum others including stalwarts of coordination chemistry like Blomstrand, Werner and Tschugaeff had already done their parts before Rây stepped in. This is probably a reason why his platinum-thioether work has not attracted as much attention as the iridium-thioether activity where Rây was the sole originator.

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